

CHEMOTHERAPEUTIC DYES. PART III. SYNTHESIS OF SUBSTITUTED AMINOPHENOTHIAZINES

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Several nitrophenothiazines containing alkyl, phenyl or ester groupings have been synthesised and catalytically reduced to aminophenothiazines with a view to testing them for their therapeutic activity.

Phenothiazines have been found to possess a variety of therapeutic activity. Antitubercular activity in phenothiazine was first pointed out by Freedlander (*Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol. Med.*, 1944, 87, 106). Several of its derivatives are well known anthelmintics (A review by Beeler and Findlay, *Bull. Natl. Formulary com.*, 1942, 10, 84), antihistamines (Gilman *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 888; Helpert *et al.*, *Compt. rend. soc. Biol.*, 1946, 140, 361, 363; Vander Brook *et al.*, *J. Pharmacol. Exptl. Therap.*, 1948, 94, 197), urinary antiseptics (De Eds and Thomas, *J. Parasitol.*, 1942, 24, 363), antiemetics (Friend and Cumins, *J. Amer. Med. Assoc.*, 1953 153, 480) and local anaesthetics (Helpert *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, p. 363; Hazard *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1949, 143, 908). The activity of these phenothiazines has been attributed to their ready oxidation to quinones. A number of aminophenothiazines containing alkyl, phenyl or ester groupings have therefore been synthesised with a view to testing them for their therapeutic activity. For this purpose, eight diphenyl sulphides were prepared by the condensation of *o*-aminothiophenol with appropriate dinitrohalogenobenzenes (B), having a reactive chlorine atom. The diphenyl sulphides were then refluxed with alcoholic 2*N* sodium hydroxide which resulted in the rearrangement and ring-closure (Bennet, 'Smiles Rearrangement', *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 4192; Massie, *Chem. Rev.*, 1954, 54, 797) yielding nitrophenothiazines.

[R = Alkyl, phenyl or ester grouping.]

The nitrophenothiazines were subsequently reduced to the corresponding amino-phenothiazines catalytically, which could only be obtained in their oxidised form, as exposure of the reduced solution to air resulted in a marked change in colour, and the bases isolated from the solution failed to respond to test for an amino group. The bases were converted into the hydrochlorides which also did not exhibit sharp melting points and were therefore characterised through their picrates.

In the course of the present work, the authors came across some cases of failure of 'Smiles rearrangement'. 2'-Amino- and 2'-amino-5-methyl-2:4-dinitrodiphenyl sulphides and 2'-amino-4-phenyl(*p*-nitro)-2:6-dinitrodiphenyl sulphide could not be rearranged even on refluxing with higher concentrations (20%) of the alkali solution. It has also been observed that substitution of alkyl or ester grouping in position-6 of the dinitrodiphenyl sulphide facilitates the Smiles rearrangement.

EXPERIMENTAL

Substituted Diphenyl Sulphides.—The substituted dinitrochlorobenzene (0.02 *M*) and *o*-aminothiophenol (0.02 *M*) were suspended in ethanol (20 c.c.) and approximately 2 *N* sodium acetate solution (12 c.c.) added to it. On refluxing the mixture under stirring for 4 hours over a steam-bath, the diphenyl sulphide separated out as a red or reddish brown mass which was filtered and recrystallised from acetic acid.

The melting points, yields and analyses of the diphenyl sulphides obtained are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Diphenyl sulphide (A for 2'-amino-).	M. P.	% Yield.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.
1.	A-5-Carbomethoxy-2:4-dinitro-	171°	93.0 %	11.69	12.04
2.	A-6-Carbomethoxy-2:4-dinitro-	182°	88.0	11.32	11.57
3.	A-4-Carbomethoxy-2:6-dinitro-	176°	82.6	11.28	11.57
4.	A-5-Methyl-2:4-dinitro-	96°	78.3	12.67	13.16
5.	A-6-Phenyl-2:4-dinitro-	154°	76.3	11.20	11.44
6.	A-4(<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl)-2:6-dinitro-	185°	85.0	13.42	13.59
7.	A-6-Methyl-2:4-dinitro-	240°	70.0	13.50	13.77
8.	A-5-Methyl-2:4-dinitro-	175°	91.7	13.52	13.77

Nitrophenothiazines.—To a suspension of the diphenyl sulphide (0.015 *M*) was added 2 *N*-NaOH solution (15 c.c.) and the mixture refluxed under stirring. The colour of the reaction mixture darkened immediately on the addition of the alkali solution. After stirring for about half an hour, the nitrophenothiazine separated out as a dark reddish brown solid which was filtered, washed with dilute caustic soda, followed by a little ethanol, and recrystallised from acetic acid.

The melting points, yields and analyses of the nitrophenothiazines, thus prepared, are shown in Table II.

TABLE II.

No.	Phenothiazines:	M. P.	% Yield.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.
1.	1-Carbomethoxy-3-nitro-	192°	92.0	8.88	9.27
2.	1-Carbomethoxy-3-nitro-	200°	94.5	8.48	8.86
3.	3-Carbomethoxy-1-nitro-	150°	86.4	8.55	8.86
4.	2-Ethyl-3-nitro-	178°	85.3	10.36	10.20
5.	1-Phenyl-3-nitro-	194°	28.0	8.86	8.75
6.	1-Methyl-3-nitro-	204°	84.0	10.96	10.85

Reduction of the Nitrophenothiazines.—The nitrophenothiazine (1 g.), suspended in glacial acetic acid (30 c.c.), was reduced in an atmosphere of hydrogen (50 lbs. pressure) for 4 hours using Adams' catalyst (50 mg.). A light green or brown coloured solution was obtained on reduction, which darkened on exposure to air. The reduced solution was quickly filtered and concentrated in vacuum to approximately 10 c.c. On neutralising the solution with ammonium hydroxide, the base separated out.

The base was dissolved in benzene and converted into the hydrochloride by passing dry HCl gas through the dry benzene solution.

On addition of a saturated aqueous picric acid solution to the filtered aqueous solution of the imine hydrochloride, picrate separated out as a green or yellow precipitate which was washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol.

The melting points and analyses of the picrates obtained from the iminophenothiazines are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

S. No.	Phenothiazine.	M. P.	% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.
1.	3-Amino-1-carbomethoxy-	162°	14.25	14.03
2.	3-Amino-1-carbomethoxy-	178°	13.72	13.64
3.	1-Amino-3-carbomethoxy-	220°	13.50	13.64
4.	3-Amino-1-phenyl-	* 155°	13.36	13.54
5.	3-Amino-2-ethyl-	* 245°	15.22	14.92
6.	3-Amino-1-methyl-	* 140°	15.50	15.38

*Melts with decomposition.

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